

Reuse of FAIR2Adapt Visual Materials by External Projects and Initiatives

Communication & Dissemination Guidelines

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1. Purpose

In alignment with FAIR2Adapt's commitment to the FAIR principles, this guideline establishes a transparent approach to the reuse of FAIR2Adapt visual materials by external projects, initiatives, and organisations.

The objective is to:

- promote broad dissemination and reuse,
- reduce administrative barriers to collaboration,
- ensure appropriate acknowledgement of FAIR2Adapt and contributing partners,
- maintain compliance with EU visibility requirements.

2. Scope

Unless explicitly marked otherwise, this guideline applies to visual materials produced within FAIR2Adapt, including:

- graphics and infographics
- images and figures

- presentation slides
- videos and animations
- promotional and social media visuals

3. Attribution Requirements

FAIR2Adapt visual materials can be openly reused without prior permission, provided that proper attribution is given and materials are used in a manner consistent with their original context.

When reusing FAIR2Adapt visuals, external users should:

- clearly acknowledge the source using wording such as: “Visual from the FAIR2Adapt project (EU-funded).”
- retain, where possible:
 - FAIR2Adapt branding elements,
 - EU funding acknowledgement included in the original material.

Attribution responsibility rests with the reusing party.

4. Adaptation and Modification

FAIR2Adapt visual materials may be adapted for reuse, including resizing, reformatting, or incorporation into derivative dissemination materials.

When adaptations are made, the reusing party should clearly indicate that the material has been modified, for example, by including wording such as: “Adapted from the FAIR2Adapt project (EU-funded).”

Adaptations should not misrepresent the original meaning, results, or context of the material. Reuse or adaptation of FAIR2Adapt visuals does not imply endorsement by the FAIR2Adapt consortium unless explicitly stated.

5. Exceptions

Some visuals may contain third-party content or partner-specific ownership restrictions. Where reuse limitations apply, materials will be clearly marked (e.g., “Reuse requires permission”).

6. Responsibility

The FAIR2Adapt communication team:

- makes materials openly available,
- provides guidance where requested,
- does not require routine approval of reuse requests.

External users are responsible for correct attribution and appropriate use.

7. Contact Point

The FAIR2Adapt communication team acts as the coordination contact for reuse requests. Please reach out to Lauren Snyder (lauren.snyder@tib.eu) with questions and requests.

8. Review

This guideline may be updated as collaboration practices evolve.